

*****Overview*****

This GPS dataset is processed to study the time-lag effects of ionospheric response to severe geomagnetic storms on kinematic precise point position (PPP) solution degradation using GNSS stations distributed worldwide.

The dataset description for the geomagnetic storm during September 7-8, 2017 is given as follows.

-Folder '09072017PositionError'

-Folder '09082017PositionError'

Those above folders contain the files including GPS PPP errors for GNSS stations on September 7-8, 2017. The dataset format is consistent among files.

Each column (from left to right) in the file represents:

Year

Month

Day of Month

Hour

Minute

Second

Position error in East component (unit: meter)

Position error in North component (unit: meter)

Position error in Up component (unit: meter)

-Folder '09072017ROTI'

-Folder '09082017ROTI'

Those above folders contain the files including the rate of change of total electron content (TEC) index (ROTI) derived from the GPS stations on September 7-8, 2017. The dataset format is consistent among files. Each column (from left to right) in the file represents:

Year

Month

Day of Month

Hour

Minute

Second

Day of Year

Elevation angle (unit: degree)

Azimuth angle (unit: degree)

Geographic Latitude of Ionospheric Pierce Point at 350 km (unit: degree)

Geographic Longitude of Ionospheric Pierce Point at 350 km (unit: degree)

Biased TEC (unit: TECu)

Rate of TEC (unit: TECu/s)

ROTI (unit: TECu/min)

PRN ID of the GPS satellite

The dataset uploaded for the St. Patrick's Day storm during March 17–18, 2015, can be accessed at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3733846>.